

MEETING THE IDUSTRY NEEDS: UNDERSTANDING THE CAREER PREFERENCES OF ISLAND GRADE 10 STUDENTS

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Abstract

The choice of a career is one that is made while a student is in the perplexed condition that is common during their senior year of high school. For a proposed career guidance program, this study should identify the preferred SHS track, preferred career, and factors influencing career choice among grade 10 island students at San Agustin National High School in San Agustin, Madridejos, Cebu. It should also identify the needs of the industry in Bantayan Island. The DepEd Tool for Career Offering in Senior High School and Career Evaluation research questionnaire was distributed to the students' responses using a descriptive survey. The respondents from the industry received a research-made questionnaire to identify the number of employees and/or workers they needed. The results then revealed that the pupils preferred technical-vocational and livelihood track was cooking, while their favorite academic track was general academic strand as their course in senior high school program. Interest and specialization, early inspiration, and in-demand jobs are the variables that influence students while choosing a career. Students in grade 10 at San Agustin National High School choose the General Academic Strand in Senior High School over any other track. However, the community's demands for the industry are more focused on TVL-related jobs. As a result, the island students' intended career path does not match what the business requires. To help learners choose a job that is in line with the demands of the community, a career guidance program has been proposed in light of this.

Keywords: Career guidance program, Career preferences, Industry needs, Island grade 10 students, preferred senior high school track

INTRODUCTION

Every person has the choice to choose a preferred career. In the senior year of high school, students must make a decision in a perplexing position regarding their career inclinations. He may rely on his friends and family if he is unable to make his own decisions or is not yet prepared to enroll in college. One's career choice may be influenced by a variety of factors. Students who make a wise profession choice may be able to lead happy and fulfilling lives. They are able to raise a wholesome family. These numerous factors demonstrate how important a career is to students' daily lives. A student can have an idea of where to apply for a job that suits their talents and abilities if they have a career choice in mind. Even before they finish their education, they can contact businesses with letters of interest. They can easily apply for any open positions in a variety of industries. According to Tiedeman, as ego-relevant crises are overcome, professional development takes place as part of the overall process of cognitive development. He went on to say that making decisions is a continual process and that people

can change their professional paths at any time by removing themselves from a situation or environment. When a student is confused about their course, for example, they may feel less enthusiastic about that particular field. They then decide to change to a different school or take a different course that better suits their interests. Additionally, if a person has trouble making decisions, they may repeat these confused techniques until they earn a new bachelor's degree, which can seriously interfere with their ability to find employment in the future if they are not happy and fulfilled with the path they have chosen. In order to give graduates, the necessary information, abilities, and attitudes to compete in the global market, the number of years that students spent in high school was increased by two at the beginning of the K–12 Curriculum. The Senior High School (SHS) program was made available across the entire country. In various schools, multiple tracks are available. The track options that the schools offer is determined by what is approved by the higher office and by the needs of the local industry. Some of the SHS students' job preferences are not met by these, while others are. The grade 10 pupils at San Agustin National High School are hesitant and confused about the track they want to choose. They don't know enough about the various employment options. They struggle to see their future selves or the person they aspire to become. They aren't sure if they'll continue their studies in college or merely look for work when they graduate from junior high school. General Academic Strand (GAS) and the Technical-Vocational Livelihood Track, Specifically Cookery, are the courses offered at San Agustin National High School. Some of the grade 10 students seem to like these two options for whatever reason. Some claim that their family or other relatives are a major influence, while others attribute it to the community's high demand for certain occupations and their early expectations. The researcher was interested in learning whether community needs were met by the preferred careers. In light of the study's findings, the researcher is considering developing a career advising program that would cater to the needs of SHS students.

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

This study is based on John Holland's (1997) Vocational Choice Theory, which emphasizes an individual's professional progression. He claimed that people project their personal and professional perspectives onto job titles and choose careers that fit their own preferences. Self-perception theory and social stereotyping are just two of the constructs from personality psychology, work behavior, and social psychology that are included in this theory. The theory of occupational choice, which entails identifying two or three dominant personality types in individuals and then matching each type with the requirements of various occupations. According to the hypothesis, there is a greater chance of favorable career outcomes, such as satisfaction, perseverance, and achievement, the higher the degree of congruence between personal traits and occupational features. Holland's theory of occupational choice is thus used by any career development expert to evaluate an individual's interest profiles from three main angles. They are distinction, consistency, and coherence. Holland further argued that these elements are related to an individual's personality and work-related outlook being clear and focused. By using this idea, which entails transforming a person's Holland profile into occupational possibilities for further examination, a profile is examined in the way that they

are typically a forerunner to a career growth. Students choose their lifetime careers based on the career preferences theory. For students to be informed and successful in their chosen careers, they must be aware of the various elements affecting their profession.

Figure 1: Schematic Diagram of the Theoretical Framework of the Study

Additionally, the Republic Act 10533, generally known as the Basic Education Act of 2012, provides assistance for this study. An Act Strengthening the Philippine Education System by Increasing the Years of Basic Education and Strengthening the Curriculum. The Enhanced Basic School Program, which includes at least one year of kindergarten, six years of elementary education, and six years of secondary education, is mandated under Section 4 of R.A. 10533. Four years of junior high school and two years of senior high school make up this secondary education. Students may choose a speciality at the senior high school based on their aptitude, interests, and the available space in the school. The curriculum of the subjects' pupils will take in Grades 11 and 12 may be determined by the school through the selection of a career track. These courses are part of the career pathways or core curriculum. Every educational organization needs to facilitate preparation for both schooling and employment. In order to develop themselves to their full potential, students must choose a subject of study that fits their capacity, aptitude, and interests. The curriculum for senior high school includes eight subject areas that are comparable to college courses. Academic track, science and technology, engineering, and mathematics, general academic strand, technical vocational and lifestyle, sport and design, and are some of them. SHS students can choose a route based on how they plan to use their education after high school. SHS offers various options but cannot guarantee employment. To ensure that graduates have the necessary knowledge to be hired, standard requirements will be applied. To get better jobs and prospects, they can also apply for TESDA

Certificates of Competency and National Certificates. SHS students can gain experience while they are in school, and after graduation, businesses may even hire them. Similarly, entrepreneurship courses have been incorporated into SHS curricula to prepare students to launch their own businesses rather than seek employment. However, evaluations of pupils' strengths and interests will be conducted. These comprise an ability test, a career assessment exam, and a high school occupational interest inventory. Activities promoting careers will also be carried out to assist students in selecting their track or specialism. However, at the start of the SHS program, the school's offerings shape the students' career preferences. Not all schools offered each of the SHS curriculum's tracks. The likelihood that graduates will find employment in a neighbouring industry largely determines what programs are offered in schools. In both public and private schools around the world, a variety of tracks are available. Global economic crises, including socioeconomic, political, and financial crises, have a significant impact on the nation. Filipinos are imaginative, creative, and ingenious despite all of these challenges. They are strong and overcome all challenges in their daily lives. Businesses that are impacted by these issues are also forced to reduce their workforces, which is referred to as a "recession." Some of them still have unfilled positions that present fresh chances for college graduates and even SHS graduates. Additionally, this job opening presents a fresh challenge in their lives, putting a great deal of responsibility in their hands so that they may one day support their families. They can make an effort to become wealthy. Uses the information and abilities they have acquired to do their jobs and acts as a supporter of industry to help the nation's declining economy. Product markets have an impact on the labour demand and skill needs in the market, which are determined by employer preferences. The employer created jobs that depend on non-routine duties, delegation, and technological substitution. Additionally, potential employees and job candidates have a variety of knowledge, competencies, and skills that can be generically categorized as skills or the results of a person's decisions in terms of their education, training, and work experience, as well as their intrinsic preferences and abilities. A highly skilled worker is needed in many businesses nowadays. They require personnel who can work independently and who can be relied upon to complete the task at hand. Excellent verbal, functional, and cognitive skills give workers the chance to succeed in any chosen field. Most Filipino graduates, according to the news on TV Patrol, have poor language abilities, which is one of the reasons they can't land jobs that are right for them. To get a job, graduates must meet the strict requirements of various businesses. The advancement of one's career is impacted by career guidance programs. Students must receive guidance when choosing their careers. The decision of a career depends on your financial ability to support the costs of obtaining formal education to prepare for it. CGP will provide Grade 10 students with information to help them choose their desired SHS track. This gives the student the chance to see how important it is to select a course that matches both their interests and the resources and job prospects that are now available. To avoid a mismatch between their talents and the current job market, students in school must be led in their chosen vocation. Students in grade 10 have the option of choosing any track at SHS, including the regular academic, technical-vocational, sports, and design tracks. Various variables influence their choosing. The choice of the student's desired career is requested. They might have a choice from the four paths the SHS program offers. They will study subjects like core subjects, applied

subjects, and specialized courses depending on the chosen program. There are several subjects available that need students to take prerequisite courses before moving on to related coursework. The researcher will consider developing a career advisory program to assist SHS students in pursuing their goals of being successful in their field of endeavour in light of the relationship between the career preferences of grade 10 students and the local industry demands.

STATEMENT OF PURPOSE

The main purpose of the study was to determine the career preferences of Grade 10 students of San Agustin National High School, District of Madridejos, and Division of Cebu Province during the school year 2017 – 2018 and the industry needs nearby for a proposed career guidance program. Specifically, it answered to the following sub-problems: What is the preferred career track of Grade 10 students? Academic Track; Technical - Vocational Track; Sports Track; Arts and Design Track? What are the factors that influence the career preference of the grade 10 students? Personal Peer or friends; Significant People; and in - demand job what are the needs of the industry in the locality? What is the degree of alignment between the preferred career track of the students and the needs of the industry?

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research design, study environment, study participants, instrument, data collection techniques, and data analysis are all covered in this chapter. Additionally, it discusses the study's ethical implications.

DESIGN

This study will apply descriptive correlational design as a quantitative research strategy. It is quantitative because it places a focus on measurements and statistical or numerical analysis of data gathered through surveys and questionnaires. A correlational research design examines the link between or among two or more pertinent variables. Additionally, the term "descriptive correlational approach" refers to a style of research in which data is gathered without altering the topic. In this study, the industrial job needs in the community will be compared to the career references of the grade 10 pupils.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

These are the options for careers included in the K–12 curricula. The school may have provided a variety of tracks so that students may choose what they wanted to do with their lives after graduation.

Table 1: The variety of tracks available

TRACK	No. responses	Percentage
Academic	149	88
Technical voc.	20	12
Sports	0	0
Arts and design	0	0
Total	169	100

The academic track is the one that Senior High School students choose the most frequently out of all the available tracks, according to the table. Since this is offered at the school and a neighboring school on the island, the majority of respondents chose it. The findings indicate that no pupils in grade 10 chose sports and the arts and design. Since these are not offered at the school or even on the entire island of Bantayan, no one picks sports, the arts, or design. Since this course is not offered in the municipality, students who want to enroll in it can travel to Cebu City. Connected to Gubalane's (2016) claim that not all strands and tracks are available in every school in every region. Students must therefore consider what is accessible to them in terms of priority. The fact that GAS is the only academic track strand without a clearly defined professional route suggests that learners favour GAS because they are still unsure of which track, they will pursue in the future. The academic track's course offerings are crucial for learners since they set them up for their future endeavours. The course's three exits—trabaho, kolehiyo, and negosyo—give students the chance to pursue their interests. Only 12% of Grade 10 pupils said they preferred TVL Track. The TVL track's offers are crucial for meeting the demands of the island municipality's students. It gives the students the abilities they'll need for their future plans. To help students prepare for the National Certificate, TVL offers them additional skills.

Table 2: An array of strand for the career choice of the students

Academic Track > Strand	No. of Students who Preferred the different track and strand	No. of Students who choose the career under the different track and strand
GAS	87	74
ABM	41	32
HUMMS	11	21
STEM	10	10
Total	149	137
TVL >Strand		
PC Hardware and Servicing	1	0
Automotive	1	0
Bread and Pastry	2	0
Welding	3	0
Electronics	2	0
Cookery	4	32
Housekeeping	2	0
Tourism	1	0
Computer Animation	1	0
Front Office Servicing	1	0
Horticulture	1	0
Food and Beverage Service	1	0
Total	20	32

The preferred career of the Grade 10 students.

This selection of strands from the several tracks helps the students decide what to study in accordance with their needs, abilities, and talents. According to Table 2, students in grade 10 chose careers in academics, TVL, sports, arts, and design. Only 74 of the 87 students who favored the General Academic Strand registered and chose this as their desired career, according to the results. Then, 21 of the 11 students who liked HUMMS chose to enroll and pursue this field of study. Initially, just 4 students favored TVL, but 32 chose this field as their career. Additionally, no pupils expressed interest in jobs in the fields of sports, the arts, or design. Additionally, nobody wants to consider a profession in the arts, sports, or design. Even while students excel in athletics, coaching, music, dancing, and theater, many do not wish to pursue careers in these fields.

Factors that influence the Career Preference of the Students

The students identified factors affecting their career choice. This includes child aspiration, family and relatives, peer and friends, interest and specialization and in demand job. The result is presented in Table 3.

Indicators	WM	DE
Personal		
1. My preference of course is a reflection of my talent.	4.33	Strongly Agree
2. My preference of course is my personal choice.	4.28	Strongly Agree
3. My preferred course is my childhood dream and work.	3.99	Agree
4. My parents are the ones who are choosing my course.	2.82	Moderately Agree
5. The dominant profession in my family and relatives is also my preferred course.	2.80	Moderately Agree
6. Our family business is a factor in my choice of course.	2.36	Disagree
Peer or Friends		
1. My preferred course is the preferred course of my friend	2.49	Disagree
2. My friend's choice of school affects my decision in choosing my course.	2.46	Disagree
3. I am influence by my friends.	2.28	Disagree
In demand job		
1. I consider the work I will get after finishing my studies in choosing a course.	3.67	Agree
2. The availability of job in the future affects my choice of course	3.60	Agree
3. I consider my course to be an in - demand course	3.41	Agree

Legend:

4.21 - 5.00 - Strongly Agree

3.41 - 4.20 - Agree

2.61 - 3.40 - Moderately Agree

1.81 - 2.60 - Disagree

1.00 - 1.80 - Strongly Disagree

As reflected in table 4, the factors that influence the career preference of the Grade 10 students in San Agustin National High School. It shows that interest and specialization, childhood inspiration, and in-demand job were considered as factors that influence the students in choosing the career. This means that the students prefer their career choice because it is their

personal choice and reflection from their talents. Moreover, they preferred their career choice as their childhood dream. Furthermore, they select the career because of the job in the future and the demand of course after they finish their studies. This implies that the learners are wise enough in choosing their career preference because they select best of their capacity and ability as well as the demand of work after their graduation. The learners are old enough because they are no longer influence by their parents in the choice of course. The parents support to their children because they intensify their learning on the awareness and advocacy campaign initiated by the school. Gone are the days that the parents and sponsors are the one who will choose for the course that their children will take up.

Needs of Industry

The industry nearby the school vicinity has different needs of worker. This would probably the job opportunity for the students whenever they will graduate in SHS program. The different industry such as bakeshop, restaurant, resort/beach, general merchandise, bank, poultry farm, tailoring, hotels, and internet shop listed the needed workers in their company. The different establishment listed the needed workers or employees as presented in Table 5. As reflected in table 5, the needs of the nearby industry in San Agustin National High School. It reveals that the industry nearby like bakeshop, restaurant, resort, general merchandize, bank, poultry, tailoring, hotels, and internet shop have different needs of workers. Among this industry, the common needs of them were cashier, driver, clerk, and ordinary workers.

The outcomes shows that there were open doors for the understudies to be utilized after graduation. A large portion of the required laborers were hard abilities. As specified in Branch of Training request No. 41 s. 2015, work is one of the four ways out in SHS program. For specialized and professional vocations, understudies apply for TESDA Endorsements. Privately owned business accomplices assist understudies with acquiring work insight while examining. This experience is the very thing that we called as work submersion wherein understudies are uncovered in real work. It infers that the alumni of the SHS program have the potential chance to have some work after their graduation in light of the fact that the business close by need their aptitude. The school is supposed to foster the abilities of the students which are fundamental in the gig that they will be arrived after graduation. It is likewise considered significant that the educator ingrain great qualities toward working so students could have a superior future.

Table 5: Needs of Industry

Industry	F	%	Industry	F	%
Bakeshop	n=5		Poultry	n=5	
1. Baker	4	80	1. Farm Labor	5	100
2. Saleslady	4	80	2. Security Guard	5	100
3. Supervisor	1	20	3. Asst. Manager	5	100
4. Driver	1	20	4. Carpenter	5	100
5. Manager	1	20	5. Breeder	5	100
6. Cashier	4	80	6. Electrician	5	100
Restaurant	n=4		7. Driver	5	100
1. Chef	2	50	8. Automotive	5	100
2. Room Cleaner	4	100	9. Clerk	5	100
3. Driver	4	100	10. Salesperson	5	100
4. Front Desk	4	100	11. Farm Manager	5	100
5. Kitchen helper	4	100	Hotels	n=2	
6. Bar Man	4	100	1. Information Clerk	2	100
7. Cashier	4	100	2. Room Attendant	2	100
8. Powder Girls	4	100	3. Laundry Helper	2	100
9. Waiter	4	100	4. Powder Girl	2	100
General Merchandise	n=5		5. Cashier	1	50
1. Bookkeeper	5	100	6. Hotel Manager	1	50
2. Driver	5	100	Internet Shop	n=3	
3. Salesman/Saleslady	5	100	1. Encoder	3	100
4. Carpenter	5	100	2. Technician	3	100
5. Painter	5	100	3. Clerk	3	100
6. Welder	5	100	4. Graphic Designer	3	100
7. Store Helper	5	100	5. Operation Manager	1	33
8. Clerk	5	100			
Bank	n=3				
1. Teller	3	100			
2. Manager	3	100			
3. Security	3	100			
4. Utility	3	100			
5. Bank Cleaner	3	100			

The degree of alignment between the preferred career track of the students and the needs of the industry.

Understudies were allowed an opportunity to choose their favored vocation under specific track and the business likewise recorded their required representatives or laborer. The need of the business has been gathered by the favored profession track of the understudies. The level of arrangement between them were introduced in Table 6. Table 6, shows the level of arrangement between the favored profession track of grade 10 understudies and the required laborers in the business.

	Preferred Career Track	N	Industry Needs/Needed Workers Related to Each Track	Degree of Alignment
1	GAS	87	18	20.69 %
2	ABM	41	14	34.15 %
3	HUMMS	11	8	72.73 %
4	STEM	10	3	30.00 %
5	PC Hardware and Servicing	1	6	16.67 %
6	Automotive	1	5	20.00 %
7	Bread and Pastry	2	4	50.00 %
8	Welding	3	5	60.00 %
9	Electronics	2	5	40.00%
10	Cookery	4	26	15.38 %
11	Housekeeping	2	15	13.33 %
12	Tourism	1	0	0.00 %
13	Computer Animation	1	3	33.33 %
14	Front Office Servicing	1	10	10.00 %
15	Horticulture	1	10	10.00 %
16	Food and Beverage Service	1	6	16.67%
	Total	169	143	84.62 %

As displayed in the table, there were 87 understudies favored general scholarly strand however simply 18 positions connected with this track were required by specific industry. This suggests that there are more alumni overall scholastic strand while less laborers or occupations required. This will be the justifications for why the alumni in San Agustin Public liked to search for a task in different spots, urban communities or territory. Since the local area can't give occupations on this track. There were not many foundations or organizations which can extend employment opportunities related on this track. Moreover, for TVL related positions, there were just couple of understudies' favored TVL track. Be that as it may, more positions are required in the island of Bantayan. This shows that the popular positions in the territory were the positions connected with Specialized - Professional and Work Track.

This suggests that the students are not keen on working at ocean side hotels which are normal locally. They have no plans of chasing after the travel industry related courses for them to help their local area in advancing the places of interest in the island. Hence, the favored profession track and the business needs in the region isn't adjusted. This implies that the necessities of the business locally aren't fit to the course presenting of the school. The necessities of the local area don't meet the favored vocation track of the understudies in San Agustin Public Secondary School. Moreover, there is compelling reason need to incorporate games, expressions and configuration track in the contribution of the school since no understudies favored this track and no positions offered likewise locally.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

The remarkable discoveries of the review are examined in view of the sub-issues of the review. These are: The favored strand of the understudies in scholastic track was General Scholarly Strand as their course in SHS program and in TVL track the understudy's favored cookery. The

elements that impact the understudies in picking the vocation were interest and specialization, youth motivation, and sought-after work. The necessities of the business locally are more on TVL related positions. The favored vocation track of the understudies isn't lined up with the necessities of the business.

CONCLUSION

In light of the discoveries, it tends to be reasoned that the profession inclination of the students in San Agustin Public Secondary School isn't lined up with the business needs locally. The school has offered restricted courses that provides food the necessities of the close by industry that is laid out in the island region. Besides, the favored profession of the students is additionally connected with their inclinations and ability. The outcome attested with the Professional Decision Hypothesis that individuals project self and universe of work sees onto word related titles and settle on vocation choices that fulfill their own directions.

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